

CALCULATION OF CRITICAL PRESSURE FROM BOILING POINT AND PARACHOR DATA.

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The equation, $P_c = k \frac{T_b}{[P]}$, has been proposed for calculating the critical pressures from the boiling point and parachor data of various liquids.

Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1177; "The Parachor and Valency", 1930, p. 31) has compared parachors and molecular critical volumes and has shown that the ratio of the parachor $[P]$ to the molecular critical volume (V_c) of a given compound has an almost constant value of 0.77 for all substances. Hence,

$$V_c = \frac{[P]}{0.77}$$

According to Van der Waals, "at their critical points, the values of $P_c V_c / T_c$ should be the same for all substances" (*vide*, Young, "Stoichiometry," 1918, p. 207). So $P_c V_c / T_c = r_c$, where r_c is a constant. This statement is true only when the molecules of an ordinary substance undergo no alteration during the process of liquefaction. When molecular association takes place as with acetic acid, alcohols, etc., the relation between temperature, pressure and volume becomes much more complex (*cf.* Young, *ibid.* p. 189).

The mean value of r_c as calculated from the data for twenty-five different substances (Young, *ibid.* p. 170) is 1625, when pressures and volumes are expressed in cm. and c.c. respectively. These values are incorporated in the following table.

Substituting for V_c and r_c , the above equation becomes,

$$\frac{P_c \times \frac{[P]}{0.77}}{T_c} = 1625.$$

Rewriting,
$$P_c = 1625 \times 0.77 \times \frac{T_c}{[P]}.$$

According to this equation,

$$P_c = 1251 \times \frac{T_c}{[P]},$$

if the known values of critical pressures are plotted against the corresponding values of the ratios of critical temperatures to the parachors, a straight line graph should be obtained with a slope of 1251.

CALCULATION OF CRITICAL PRESSURE FROM BOILING POINT, ETC. 367

Substance.	B. p. T_b .	$T_c/[P]$.	Critical pressure P_c obs.	calc.	$\frac{P_c V_c}{T_c} = r_c$.
Ditsobutyl	382.2	1.594	1866 cm.	2162 cm.	1636
n-Octane	308.8	1.624	1873	2222	1612
n-Heptane	371.4	1.746	2043	2344	1654
Ditsopropyl	331.1	1.852	2336	2447	1665
n-Hexane	342.0	1.880	2251	2471	1627
isoPentane	301.0	2.001	2502	2551	1668
n-Pentane	309.2	2.042	2510	2620	1654
Methyl isobutyrate	365.3	2.130	2574	2808	1613
Ethyl propionate	372.0	2.144	2522	2263	1590
Propyl acetate	374.6	2.145	2523	2855	1585
Methyl butyrate	375.8	2.183	2606	2888	1598
Ether	307.6	2.205	2706	2836	1634
Hexamethylene	353.9	2.362	3028	2952	1681
Ethyl acetate	350.2	2.410	2888	3148	1580
Methyl propionate	342.7	2.458	3003	3190	1595
Propyl formate	353.9	2.489	3046	3196	1612
Carbon tetrachloride	349.8	2.530	3218	3104	1697
Iodobenzene	461.5	2.574	3391	3214	1650
Chlorobenzene	405.0	2.595	3393	3247	1652
Bromobenzene	429.0	2.606	3391	3949	1638
Fluorobenzene	358.2	2.613	3391	3265	1643
Benzene	353.2	2.722	3640	3342	1660
Methyl acetate	330.1	2.846	3521	3617	1581
Ethyl formate	327.3	2.867	3554	3603	1601
Methyl formate	304.9	3.527	4503	4309	1590
Mean					1625

It is observed that the mean value of $T_c/T_b = 1.56$, where T_b is the boiling point of a substance. So, $T_c = 1.56 T_b$. Substituting this value of T_c in the above equation,

$$P_c = 1251 \times 1.56 \times \frac{T_b}{[P]} = 1952 \times \frac{T_b}{[P]},$$

or

$$P_c = k \cdot \frac{T_b}{[P]}$$

where k is a constant, the magnitude of which depends upon the units employed in expressing the pressures and volumes.

Expressing in a general manner, the critical pressure of a substance is given by the ratio of its boiling point to its parachor multiplied by a constant.

The applicability of this equation can be well illustrated by the values calculated for twenty-five different substances given. It can be observed from the table that the calculated values are in quite good agreement with the observed values (due to Young, *loc. cit.*) considering the fact that various approximations are employed in deducing the equation.

These calculations, besides lending further support to Sugden's theory that the parachor is really equivalent to a molecular volume, are useful for quickly estimating the critical pressures of various substances without actually performing any experiment regarding the critical phenomena. Further, this calculation is a rough guide in the actual determination of critical pressure which is by no means easily observable; the boiling point and parachor data are readily available from literature.

Some of the deviations observed can be attributed to the deviation of the actual value of T_c/T_b from the mean value of 1.56. More correct results may be obtained if the following corrections are introduced:

- (i) For the higher members of the homologous series, $T_c/T_b = 1.45$.
- (ii) For elements, like chlorine, bromine, oxygen, argon etc.,
 $T_c/T_b = 1.75$.

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